

Report on the first NFDI Metadata Workshop

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Metadata is a topic of significant interest across all consortia, serving as a crucial link between them. When properly addressed, it enables consortia to share their specific needs and experiences, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange.

This report summarizes the outcomes of the first NFDI Metadata Workshop, which took place on January 14-15, 2025, in Dresden, and was organized by the Taskforce Metadata. The workshop marked the beginning of a series of NFDI-wide metadata discussions aimed at developing joint recommendations for metadata schemas for datasets and the use of re3data as a central registry for repositories.

1 Introduction

To ensure that research data can be efficiently found and reused, it must be described with metadata. Metadata provides essential information about datasets, such as details about the researchers who collected the data and the licensing terms under which it can be used. The [Taskforce Metadata](#) addresses key challenges in metadata and research data management, focusing on:

- Harmonizing metadata across disciplines to enhance findability.
- Establishing general data and metadata standards to support an NFDI core metadata format.
- Facilitating format conversions and ensuring integration with persistent identifier systems.

The primary goal is to promote the use and adoption of existing and newly developed cross-disciplinary terminologies and metadata schemas. By improving interoperability between consortia, the taskforce aims to fulfill the requirements outlined in the [Bund-Länder-Vereinbarung \(BLV\)](#) while adhering to the formal obligations set by the NFDI association statutes.

The BLV emphasizes the need for transdisciplinary metadata standards to ensure the broad (re)usability of research data. This initiative aligns with the [NFDI Strategy 2025/2026](#) and the White Paper [Umgang mit Zielen der BLV als Grundlage für die Strukturevaluation](#), which call for standardizing diverse metadata formats across disciplines to enhance the efficiency of the entire scientific system.

This report presents the results of the first Taskforce Metadata workshop, held on 14-15 January 2025 in Dresden, that initiated a process to create a comprehensive portfolio of metadata schemas to establish a solid foundation for implementing the FAIR principles across NFDI consortia, to assess required metadata fields across different schemas as input for a cross-consortia metadata core profile.

Moreover, the workshop initialised discussions on an NFDI-wide recommendation for the registration and continuous updating of research data repositories in *re3data*.

2 Workshop Programme

The two-day workshop agenda was designed to maximize the exchange of ideas for developing a joint recommendation on common metadata schemas for datasets. It focused on consortias' needs and practices, potential metadata schema candidates, and specific fields for inclusion in the recommendation.

The in-person workshop provided a valuable opportunity to discuss metadata recommendations across different consortia. To facilitate this, we chose interactive workshop methods that encouraged both feedback from the consortia and meaningful exchanges between them.

Introduction and Impulses

The introduction session was implemented as a plenary session and included a welcome, introductions to the breakouts, and invited talks to provide key insights as stimuli for the following discussions (see slides in Appendix). We invited *re3data* to present an overview of the registry of research data repositories, particularly on the updated metadata schema and related NFDI requirements, e.g., for improving properties on metadata schemas and name APIs more specifically. Additionally, we invited a speaker to offer an EOSC perspective on similar initiatives at the European level.

- Welcome and Introduction from the Taskforce Metadata Group (Thorsten Trippel, Leibniz-Institut für Deutsche Sprache/Text+, and Christin Henzen, TU Dresden/NFDI4Earth)

- Overview and “Lessons Learned” from EOSC Services/Datasource Profiles” (Mark Dietrich, EGI Foundation/EOSC Beyond)
- The institutional process to pass an official NFDI Standard (Stefanie Fuchsloch, NFDI Office)
- re3data – Updates from the registry and service schema (Charlotte Neidiger, KIT/re3data)

Investigating the Standards

In preparing the workshop, the Taskforce Metadata investigated possible candidates, which served as a starting point for the discussion. When reviewing established metadata schemas for datasets, mappings, and existing implementations of relevant services—such as data sources and aggregators—we identified the most frequently used schemas - [DCAT](#), [DataCite](#), and [schema.org](#) - as potential recommendation candidates for discovery and documentation. In this session, we sought feedback from the consortia on the three candidate schemas, focusing on how they are used, their advantages, and their limitations.

Furthermore, we identified [re3data](#) as a strong candidate for an NFDI-wide recommendation for registering repository metadata with a [structured schema](#). This is due to its extensive coverage of existing repositories, its recognition across various research communities, and its ability to facilitate comprehensive analysis of NFDI-relevant repositories. We thus asked the participants to identify issues and obstacles and provide potential benefits to recommending the usage of re3data.

The session began with pitches highlighting the key characteristics and usage examples of the three candidate schemas, and re3data. This was followed by a World Café-style discussion, where we gathered feedback from the consortia.

A [World Café](#) is a structured process for sharing knowledge and well-known conversation format, where participants engage in discussions at small(er) tables. In our workshop, we set up four tables—three dedicated to the metadata schema candidates and one to re3data. The discussion was structured into four rounds, ensuring that all participants had the opportunity to visit each table.

Table hosts guided the conversations, encouraging participants to share their general experiences with the schemas, discuss how their consortia use them, and evaluate their advantages and limitations. For the re3data table, the host encouraged participants to share their experiences and needs regarding the use of re3data. The discussion also focused on identifying challenges and obstacles in developing an NFDI-wide recommendation for registering relevant repositories in re3data.

- DCAT (Jonas Grieb, Senckenberg Gesellschaft für Naturforschung/NFDI4Earth)
- DataCite (Andreas Czerniak, Bielefeld University Library)
- schema.org (Leyla Jael Castro, ZB Med/NFDI4DataScience)
- re3data (Emanuel Söding, GEOMAR/NFDI4Earth)

Towards an NFDI Metadata Core Profile

In this session, we explored the possibility of developing an NFDI core metadata profile, assuming it could be implemented using one of the previously discussed metadata standards. Specifically, we focused on identifying potential metadata fields for the core profile, building on the [RDA-developed](#)

an infrastructure to register repositories by the Helmholtz Association and by NFDI consortia such as NFDI4Earth. Taking advantage of the broad membership of NFDI consortia, and to improve the discoverability, trustworthiness, and reusability of research data repositories for the scientific communities it was suggested to formulate an NFDI-Standard, which recommends NFDI-wide registration and at least annual curation of affiliated repositories in re3data. NFDI standards are agreements adopted by the assembly of consortia for the whole of the NFDI. This NFDI Standard would ensure that the re3data information of NFDI-relevant and -recommended repositories remains **high quality, comprehensive, and up-to-date** and encourages repositories to adopt and document up-to-date practices and standards.

Overall, the feedback was very positive, with re3data seen as a natural and obvious tool for the research data landscape. The workshop also showed that while everyone was aware of re3data, not all participants actively used it. It was clarified that re3data plays an important role in facilitating cross-community information exchange by centralizing repository listings. A key strength of re3data highlighted during the workshop was the **profile feature**, which allows the creation of repository sets for specific consortia or NFDI initiatives. The Helmholtz Association is already using the profile feature, to identify its repositories. Participants suggested that NFDI could encourage the use of such profiles, potentially motivating communities to improve the curation of their repository metadata.

Several concerns regarding the use of re3data were raised as well. E.g., adding information to the registry might be challenging. Also, some communities may not perceive sufficient value in registering their repositories, especially if doing so involves significant effort. This could in particular be a challenge, when managing a large number of repositories. There were also concerns about the definition of the term "repository," which could conflict with re3data's review criteria. Additionally, some communities already maintain their own repository registries, for whom an added value benefit of re3data was not necessarily obvious. Finally, some participants discussed other alternative repository registries like e.g. FAIRsharing.

As a result of the discussions, it was decided to clarify the draft NFDI Standard proposal to reflect the feedback from the community. Workshop participants proposed several potential technical enhancements to re3data. These included developing automated methods to retrieve repository information from standardized sources, and enabling the export of badges to Wikidata to create Wikipedia infoboxes. Suggestions also focused on improving usability and classification, such as clearer distinctions between repositories and groups, identifying topical profiles, and enhancing the search functionality. Additionally, participants recommended revisiting and clarifying the definition of a data repository to ensure alignment across communities.

The next action will be that NFDI TF Metadata will improve the NFDI Standard proposal. We will also enter into a dialogue with re3data to discuss the curation process of NFDI repository information in re3data as well as the suggested improvements. We will frequently update the community on the progress of this dialogue.

Metadata schema recommendations

Initiating NFDI-wide metadata discussions on three concrete, widely known and used schemas was a successful approach towards an NFDI-wide metadata schema recommendation. All three schemas, DCAT, DataCite, and schema.org, have their strengths and weaknesses, and each has its own set of

challenges and opportunities for improvement. The following findings summarize the discussions and provide a preliminary insight into the usage of consortia:

- **schema.org** is widely recognized and used, particularly for dedicated domains. It is easy to adapt and compatible with other schemas and efforts, e.g., DCAT, RO-Crates, and mapped from the NFDI core ontology¹. However, adaptations need hosting and documentation from the community proposing adaptation.
 - Examples of usage within NFDI: NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Energy, Microbiota, NFDI4Biodiversity, FAIRagro, Data Plant, NFDI4Chem; for use case: NFDI4Memory, NFDI4XCS, Punch4NFDI, MaRDI
 - Usage concerns raised by: NFDI4Health
- **DCAT** is used across some consortia. Its usage is often driven by legal aspects and required for some governmental data. DCAT Application Profiles allow to extend the schema for disciplinary and other cases. However, discovery of the application profile is limited. Major concerns address the intended granularity of data(sets).
 - Examples of usage within NFDI: NFDI4Energy, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Earth
- **DataCite** is widely adopted. The generic structure and interoperability of the schema, especially its compatibility with external aggregators, like OpenAIRE, are widely appreciated. However, it has limitations in terms of controlled vocabularies, missing metadata elements, and restrictions or costs associated with DOI registration.
 - Examples of usage within NFDI: Punch4NFDI, BERD, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Memory
 - Usage concerns raised by: NFDI4Energy

Following the metadata schema discussions, we delved into the consortia's experiences and needs, exploring the mandatory metadata fields that are essential for their work (see, e.g., Figure 2). Preliminary findings include:

- Many consortia face challenges regarding the **quality of metadata**. Although fields are mandatory as they are needed, e.g., for discovery, some data providers fill the fields with dummy data or preliminary information.
- **General information** described in **mandatory fields**, like *title*, *identifier*, *creator*, *publisher*, are widely supported by the consortia.
- Consortia provide **stronger recommendations** for specific fields, such as requiring spatial and temporal metadata for spatio-temporal data.
- Specific cases require **further clarification regarding expected content**, such as defining the *creator* for sensor-generated data, determining whether an *identifier* should be provided as a landing page with content negotiation or as a DOI, and **refining semantic distinctions**, such as the meaning of *date modified*.
- Certain fields **require adjusted mappings**, such as *includedInDataCatalog*
- **Semantics** play a crucial role, particularly in discussions on *keywords*, *subjects*, and *topic categories*-

¹ For more information about the NFDI core ontology see: <https://ise-fizkarlsruhe.github.io/nfdicore/> and <https://github.com/ISE-FIZKarlsruhe/nfdicore>

- Concrete **examples** and **best practices** foster proper implementation of the recommendations.

Figure 2: Snapshot of onsite views from the participants on four exemplary fields

A shared understanding and well-founded recommendations for metadata are essential. Despite the findings on concrete schemas, we summarized the following key takeaways:

1. **Consortia apply different criteria when selecting appropriate metadata schemas.**
Consortia prioritize metadata schemas based on various factors, including legal requirements, specific use cases, data characteristics, technologies, and institutional or funding constraints.
2. **Consortia need schema extensions covering disciplinary aspects.**
Many consortia require extensions, such as domain-specific vocabularies, to meet disciplinary needs. Some consortia even serve broad communities with diverse sub-disciplinary requirements, making it impractical to recommend a single schema.
3. **The three metadata standards, DCAT, DataCite, and schema.org, serve as a common ground for the consortia to share dataset information across communities.**
A one-size-fits-all recommendation for one schema for publishing and sharing dataset information is not feasible. The three standards, DCAT, DataCite, and schema.org, represent the lowest common denominator across consortia. The consortia can adopt at least one of them without significant implementation challenges.
4. **Mappings between the schemas are essential for cross-consortia collaborations. Existing crosswalks do not cover all consortia needs regarding dataset findability and discoverability.**
Existing crosswalks facilitate mappings between schemas. These crosswalks, e.g., the RDA crosswalk, cover some essential fields but require adjustments to better fit the NFDI context.

Summary and next steps

Active contributions from all consortia are essential for developing an NFDI-wide recommendation for metadata schemas. Based on our workshop findings and the experiences shared by the consortia, future work should focus on:

- Expanding the list of selection criteria to ensure comprehensive coverage across all consortia, taking into account especially the task-based nature of metadata supporting findability, data set documentation, and possibly other purposes.
- Establishing best practices for schema extensions to enhance cross-consortia collaboration and data sharing.
- Leveraging multidisciplinary use cases to refine mappings and foster collaboration.
- Defining strong agreements on required fields to improve findability and discoverability, especially as schema mappings often reduce the number of mandatory fields.
- Strengthening efforts on crosswalks to maintain regular updates in alignment with evolving metadata standards.

This results in a roadmap for future activities:

1. **Conceptualization on schema mappings and crosswalks:** Continue updating crosswalks as part of ongoing efforts.
2. **Community Process on an NFDI Core Metadata Profile:** Develop a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) for required fields, leading to a *Core NFDI Metadata Profile* and assess whether additional fields beyond the required ones should be included.
3. **Crowdsourcing examples and best practices:** Gather best practices for implementations, including mappings beyond the three primary schemas (DCAT, DataCite, schema.org) and recommendations for extensions.

The Taskforce invites contributions to all related future activities.